

ANALYSIS OF DETERMINANTS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF HEALTHY CLEAN-LIVING BEHAVIORS IN SCHOOL SETTINGS AT HEALTH SCIENCE HIGH SCHOOLS SIHAT BEURATA BANDA ACEH

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ABSTRACT

Background: Clean and Healthy Living Behavior is behavior or a group of behaviors carried out based on will or awareness or learning outcomes that make a person and their family able to help themselves in the field of health and play an active role in realizing public health. **Objective:** to find out the determinants of implementing clean and healthy living behavior in the school setting at the Beurata Health Science College, Banda Aceh. **Research method:** Descriptive quantitative research with a cross sectional design with a total of 288 students obtained from total sampling based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. To collect research data on the variables of knowledge, attitudes, facilities, regulations, the role of lecturers, sanctions, a questionnaire was used. Data analysis includes univariate and bivariate using chii square. **Results:** The results of the univariate test showed that 189 respondents or 75.5% of students adopted clean and healthy living behaviour, while 225 respondents or 90.5% of students had good knowledge about clean and healthy living behavior. The results of bivariate research showed that there was a relationship between knowledge and clean and healthy living behaviour, marks value=0.000 and OR = 9.561. **Conclusion:** There needs to be a semester evaluation and a technical policy regarding the monitoring mechanism for clean and healthy living behaviour among students at the Sihata Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh.

KEYWORDS: Determinants, Clean and Healthy Living Behavior, Knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Clean and Healthy Living Behaviour is behaviour or a group of behaviors carried out based on will or awareness or learning results that make a person and their family able to help themselves in the field of health and play an active role in realizing public health. Health Promotion Vision "Want to maintain and improve their health, Able to maintain and improve their health "both physically, mentally and socially so that they are economically and socially productive (*Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2011*). In accordance with the Vision of the Indonesian Ministry of Health 2019 "Forming an "Independent Healthy Community "Clean and healthy living behavior is still a special concern for the government. This can be seen from its placement as one of the indicators of health improvement achievements in the 2015-2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program. In the SDGs, clean and healthy living

behavior is a prevention strategy with a short-term impact on improving health in 3 regional settings, namely schools, families and communities.

According to Lawrence Green, factors that influence clean and healthy living behavior are divided into 3 parts, namely predisposing factors (age, level of knowledge and level of community education), enabling factors (facilities and facilities), and reinforcing factors (support from community leaders, behavior health workers, and whether or not health promotion of clean and healthy living behavior is conveyed to the community (*Anggraini et al., 2021*).

School is a place where children will learn physical skills and develop a healthy physique. The development of children during school age is part of their subsequent development, so that every slightest abnormality will reduce the quality of human resources in the future.

According to the Center for Health Promotion (2011), there are eight indicators that must be met as a condition for success in implementing a clean and healthy living behaviour program, namely washing hands with soap, prohibiting smoking in schools, consuming healthy food, throwing rubbish in its place, measuring sports activities. measured and regular, eradicating mosquito larvae regularly, and urinating and defecating in clean latrines (*Karbito & Yessiana, 2021*).

Lectures where students begin to learn to think maturely in a concrete and rational manner. At this age, students learn to develop thinking and make decisions to maintain their bodies, including health and personal hygiene, as well as a high positive relationship between physicality and achievement. Students have started to mature and can adapt to the environment and can identify the need for personal hygiene and living a clean and healthy lifestyle is very important for them.

The low level of Clean and Healthy Living Behaviour can be seen from the fact that there is still rubbish strewn around in the classroom and outside the classroom, and the lack of interest among students in using hand washing facilities in running water even though the facilities have been provided even though they are not yet complete, as well as unhealthy eating and drinking. (*Safmila & Noviyanti, 2023*). Sihat Beurata Banda Aceh College of Health Sciences (STIKes) is one of the vocational campuses consisting of two departments ATRO and APIKES. The Sihat Beurata Banda Aceh College of Health Sciences is located in the provincial capital. Students who enter the Sihat Beurata Banda Aceh College of Health Sciences come from various districts in Aceh and some even come from outside Aceh with various backgrounds, ethnicities, characters and attitudes.

Clean and Healthy Living Behaviors such as washing hands with soap and always throwing rubbish in its place, not smoking in the campus yard, these behaviors are still rarely carried out consistently by students. This means that students carry out Clean and Healthy Living Behaviour activities irregularly. The author's observations obtained data on clean and healthy living behaviour that was far from expectations because there were many shortcomings, starting from facilities such as trash cans, hand washing soap which were still lacking, as well as regulations not being implemented optimally, and sanctions already existing but not implemented. sanctions when violating.

In order to prevent and reduce various health problems, clean and healthy living behavior is needed through developing a clean and healthy lifestyle on campus. The campus, as an agent of change, is expected to have a positive influence on families and the community regarding clean and healthy living behaviour.

From the discussion that the author has discussed above, the author is interested in raising the title, namely: Analysis of the Determinants of Implementing Clean and Healthy Living Behavior in School Settings at the Sihat Beurata College of Health Sciences, Banda Aceh.

METHOD

This research used quantitative methods, carried out using a cross-sectional design with a quantitative approach to determine the determinants of implementing clean and healthy living behaviour in the school setting at the Sihat Beurata College of Health Sciences, Banda Aceh. This research has at the Sihat Beurata College of Health Sciences, Banda Aceh. The research was carried out from December 2023 to January 2024. The sample means all students and residents of the Sihat Beurata College of Health Sciences, Banda Aceh, totalling 288 people.

Research ethics have been issued by the Chair of the Health Research Ethics Committee (KEPPKN) of the Faculty of Medical Sciences, Syiah Kuala University (USK) with registration number: 1171012P. Ethical Exempted with letter number: 206/EA/FK/2023.

RESULTS

This research aims to investigate the high and low levels of students implementing clean and healthy living behaviors in a population based on a sample of 287 respondents. The method used includes data collection through surveys and analysis of respondents' understanding of a particular topic or information.

Table 1 (Frequency Distribution of Clean and Healthy Living Behaviour of Students at the Sihat Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh.)

Clean and Healthy Living Behavior	f	%
Applied	189	75.5
Not implemented	98	27.5
Total	287	100%

Based on table 1. Based on the table above, it can be seen that the distribution of Clean and Healthy Living Behavior at the Sihat Beurata Campus in Banda Aceh has a frequency of 189 respondents or 75.5%.

Table 2 (Frequency Distribution of Students' Knowledge About Clean and Healthy Living Behavior at the Sihat Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh.)

Knowledge	f	%
Good	225	90.5
Not good	62	9.5
Total	287	100%

Based on the table 2. above, it can be seen that the distribution of student knowledge about Clean and Healthy Living Behavior at the Sihat Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh, has a frequency of 225 respondents or 90.5%.

Table 3 (Relationship between Knowledge and Clean and Healthy Living Behavior at the Sihat Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh.)

Knowledge	Clean and Healthy Living Behavior				Total	OR	α	Value
	Applied		Not Implemented					
	F	%	F	%				

Good	162	77.3	63	22.7	225	100			
Not good	27	26.3	35	73.2	62	100	9,561	0.05	0,000
Amount	189	72.5	98	72.5	287	100			

Based on Table 3. above, it shows that as many as 225 respondents expressed good knowledge, 162 people (77.3%) had a desire to implement Clean and Healthy Living Behavior. The statistical test results obtained a P value = 0.000 (P. Value < α value 0.05), so there is a significant relationship between knowledge and clean and healthy living behavior at the Sihat Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh.

The results of the Chi-Square test obtained an Odds Ratio value of 9.56, meaning that good knowledge has a chance of wanting to implement clean and healthy living behavior is more than 9.56 times compared to respondents with poor knowledge 9.56 times.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Knowledge on Clean and Healthy Living behaviors

The research results show that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and clean and healthy living behaviour at the Sihat Beurata Campus, Banda Aceh. Clean and healthy living behaviour is very important in maintaining the health of individuals and society as a whole. Knowledge has a very significant role in shaping and influencing a person's behaviour related to clean and healthy living behaviour. In this context, knowledge can be interpreted as an individual's understanding of the importance of hygiene and health practices as well as an understanding of the risks that may arise if these behaviors are ignored. Knowledge is the main foundation in forming clean and healthy living behaviour. Without sufficient understanding of the importance of maintaining cleanliness and health, a person is less likely to implement clean and healthy living behaviour practices consistently.

Education is one of the main factors that influences a person's knowledge regarding clean and healthy living behaviour. Through formal and informal education, individuals are introduced to information about hygiene, health and ways to maintain a healthy body. Mass media also has a big role in disseminating information related to clean and healthy living behaviour. Through television programs, articles in newspapers, or content on social media, the public is given knowledge about the importance of clean and healthy living behaviour and ways to carry it out.

Good knowledge about clean and healthy living behaviour helps individuals to recognize health risks that may arise due to unhealthy behaviour. For example, knowledge about the dangers of bacteria and viruses can encourage someone to wash their hands more diligently and maintain a clean environment. With adequate knowledge, someone can make better decisions regarding their health. For example, someone who understands the bad effects of consuming unhealthy food will tend to prefer consuming nutritious food.

Knowledge also helps individuals to identify clean and healthy living behaviors practices that suit their needs and conditions. Everyone can have different challenges in maintaining cleanliness and health, and knowledge helps in finding the right solutions. The level of knowledge also influences a person's ability to understand complex health information. Individuals with better knowledge tend to be better able to understand medical instructions or recommendations from health experts. In addition, adequate knowledge about clean and healthy living behaviors can be a motivation for someone to change their behaviors to be healthier. When someone realizes the great benefits of maintaining a clean and healthy lifestyle, they tend to be more motivated to make changes.

On the other hand, a lack of knowledge or incorrect knowledge about clean and healthy living behaviors can be an obstacle in implementing clean and healthy living behaviors. For example, someone who is not aware of the dangers of smoking may continue the habit even though it is detrimental to their health. Knowledge can also influence a person's mindset regarding health. Individuals who have a good understanding of clean and healthy living behaviors tend to have a more positive attitude towards lifestyle changes for health. In the context of health education, it is important to provide information that is accurate and easy to understand in order to increase public knowledge about clean and healthy living behaviors. Clear and detailed information will help in forming a correct understanding.

Knowledge about clean and healthy living behaviors is not only important for individuals, but also for families and society as a whole. When family or community members have good knowledge, they can support each other in maintaining cleanliness and health. Government programs or health institutions that aim to improve clean and healthy living behaviors often provide knowledge as a main part of their interventions. By increasing public knowledge, it is hoped that more significant changes in behaviors will occur.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and research objectives, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and clean and healthy living behaviors at the Sihat Beurata Campus in Banda Aceh with a value of $P = 0.000$ and $OR = 9.561$.

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